

Multiple perspectives

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

This workshop format aims to find, examine, and understand different perspectives towards the (central) problem. It can support the identification of relevant stakeholder groups and their potential interests.

Benefits

This enhances understanding of diverse interests, conflict resolution, and synergies in proposal design. It supports better understanding of the needs of relevant stakeholder groups.

Practical recommendations

Round 1 – Initial problem definition and own perspectives (15 min)

Start by identifying and writing down the problem or issue.

Divide participants into groups of 6–8 people. Each person in the group explains their own perspective on the issue. *“As an [agricultural advisor, researcher, farmer], I am mainly concerned with [these elements] of the issue”*

Round 2 – Identification of other relevant stakeholders (5 min)

Participants are asked to identify other stakeholders that could be concerned by the issue and to write them on cards.

Round 3 – Taking different perspectives (15 min)

Each participant chooses one stakeholder card and takes 5 minutes to reflect from the perspective of that stakeholder on questions related to timeframe, expectations, the impact of the issue on their interests, understanding of the problem. After 5 minutes, everyone shares their answers, while one person makes notes with key points pertinent to the project proposal.

Round 3 – Perspective shuffle (15–30 min)

Stakeholder cards are shuffled and redistributed among the participants. Round 2 is repeated at least once, max. 2 times depending on time availability.

Round 4 – Reflection (10 min)

Take some time to reflect on results: Are all relevant stakeholder groups identified? What are similarities and differences? What did we learn? How do we take this further into the proposal?

Credit: Multiple perspectives was sourced from the Integrated Research Toolkit (<https://integrated.landcareresearch.co.nz/>)

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Work with a diversity of backgrounds

Able to recognize and work with the limitations of different organisations

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Multiple Perspectives](#)

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